

Overview of Finance Companies in Nepal

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Abstract

This paper examines the wider aspect of finance companies over the period of Mid July 1990 to Mid April 2013. In Nepal, Finance Companies has been a more important source of long-term and short term fund (mainly debt) for industry than bank loans or other sources of debt. It has been occupied third position of market share on lending (8.3%) and deposit (7.1%) in 2012. Finance companies mostly invest on import export financing. Though the total deposit and lending of finance companies to GDP ratio increased each year there needs to be done improvement to collect deposit and productive lending to enhance the growth of overall economy.

KEYWORDS: Financial Institutions, Finance Company, Non - Bank Financial Institutions, Regulatory Agency.

BACKGROUND

Economic liberalization policy of the government has encouraged the establishment and growth of finance companies in the country within a short span of time. This is in conformity to help the growth of financial sector to make the movement of the funds easily. Finance companies have come timely to meet the individual credit needs, undertake merchant banking functions and other allied functions. The special feature of finance companies is that they go to areas where commercial banks find difficult and not accessible to lend with risk. Most of the customers prefer finance companies with the notion that taking loan from finance companies although little bit costly is confident in getting the loan without passing too many procedures often that exist in commercial banks. However, at present, due to political instability and dormant role of the real sector growth, commercial banks are overlapping

the functions of the finance companies because of their concentration in consumer lending rather than going to large project financing Shrestha and Bhandari (2008). Finance companies have come into operation under the Finance Companies Act 1986. They are registered as limited companies in the office of the registrar of companies according to the provisions made in the Company Act, 1965.

At present however, there is complete restructuring of the legal provision to the extent that enactment of New Act 2063 has repealed the finance companies acts and now it is regulated by the same umbrella act. Finance companies have to follow the new guidelines and directives issued by Nepal Rastra Bank (NRB) with frequent amendments from time to time. How far this act is beneficial to the growth of finance companies and its operations is yet to be

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seen in future. More about this will be discussed later on. Finance companies fall under category 'C' according to Nepal Rastra Bank directives and after that commercial banks and development banks are put under category 'A' and 'B'.

Finance companies borrow funds from different sources. The largest part of their funds is collected from bank loans, commercial paper sales, and issues of both long-term and short-term debt in the capital market Shrestha and Bhandari (2008). Finance companies can accept time deposit of the maturity of minimum three months to maximum six years to a maximum limit of twenty times of the primary capital of the company. But, they are allowed to accept saving deposits not exceeding 2.5 times of their primary capital.

Generally, finance companies have centered their business on lending to customer. Finance companies advance loans to individuals, firms, companies or institutions. Such companies are allowed by the Act to undertake lease financing, offering credit for purchasing or construction of residential houses. They can also perform merchant banking activities with prior approval of SEBON. These companies are popular among low-income and medium class people for financing hire purchases, vehicles, machinery, tools, equipments, durable household goods etc. As a consequence of the financial liberalization policy, finance companies are growing in the Kathmandu Valley whereas their presence is also gradually growing outside the valley due to Nepal Rastra Bank directives and incentives.

The role of the finance companies is increasing both in dimensions and the coverage due to the growth of the financial sector in the economy. Finance companies borrow loanable funds with high leverage in order to meet the needs of the consumer through the help of financial conglomerates and its subsidiaries. Even the significance of assets securitization in the process of converting financial claims into securities traded in financial market.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The existence of banks and other non banking financial institutions in a formal and organized way collectively are known as financial system. Financial system can be grouped into banking and non banking financial institution. Banking institution composed of commercial bank and development bank. Non banking financial institutions comprise of development banks, finance companies, saving and credit union, insurance companies, provided fund. Few of non banking institution are engaged in accepting deposit from the public, Bhandari (2010).

Finance companies are the financial institution establish for the purpose of granting credit to the house hold or firms. They are none banking financial institutions that provide credit to the house hold to purchase consumer goods such as automobiles, furniture etc. For the business they supply short and intermediate term credit for the purpose of purchase of equipments and motors vehicles and for financing the inventories, Kohn (2007).

There is no concrete evidence when the traditional banking system introduced in Nepal, but there so many evidence of transaction of coinage since the ancient period. It is assumed that the regular history of coinage began from the 5th century. In the year 879/880 A.D., Shankhadhar shankaya introduced a new era after paying the debts that existed in the country. In 1877 A.D., Prime Minister Ranodip Shign established Tejarath Adda which was the first steps towards the institutional development of banking industry in Nepal. The basic motives of that institution were to provide credit facilities at a concessional rate to the general public. Kausitosh Khana was established during the regime of King Prithivi Narayan shah also considers other steps towards development of banking in Nepal, Sharma (2007). Banking in modern sense started with the inception of Nepal bank establish in Kartik 30, 1994. It worked as a central bank and commercial bank till the establishment of NRB. NRB was

established upon Baisakh 2013 as a central bank of Nepal under NRB act 2012. Nepal industrial development corporation was established in 2016 and then fully government owned commercial bank, ratriya banijaya bank was established in 2022 B.S. ADB was established in Magh 7, 2024, Shrestha and Bhandari (2008). After government follow liberalization policy numbers of joint venture banks are established in Nepal. The finance company act was come into existence on 2042 B.S that governs the establishment and limitation of the establishment of the finance company. It allowed the finance company to take deposit from the people and institution and make them available on hire purchase, housing and commerce. The history of finance company was begun with the establishment of Nepal housing development finance company, in 1992 A.D. During the period of 1993A.D, seven finance companies were established. There was rapid growth of the finance companies and total number becomes 28 in 1994. The act was amended after six year that was came into existence and that permits these institution to offer installment credit for the purchase of vehicles, equipments or durable goods, purchase or construction of residential buildings, for leasing financing , for operating commercial, industrial and other enterprise. Most of the finance companies are operating on the Kathmandu Valley and few are operating outside the valley Pandey (2009).

Finance company is allowed to transact in Indian currency. They are still restricted to transact on foreign currency. In order to govern bank and financial institution Banking and financial institution act 2063 came into existence that replaced all other acts. The act divided financial institution into 4 categories. Commercial banks are given A categories, development bank into B, finance company into C and other financial institution into D categories, Economic survey (2012).

Finance companies' community development activities have traditionally been directly linked to their role as financial organizations receiving deposits, extending loans and making investments, Fairbairn et al. (1997). Community development may result from innovative lending of funds to individuals or businesses. In this regard Finance companies may be well-positioned to play a critical role in entrepreneurship development and firm growth in communities. This is particularly important in rural communities because entrepreneurship is emerging as key in regional growth. At present and in the foreseeable future, an overwhelming number of jobs being created in the economy are by small business expansion and start-ups (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) 2000). Not only do entrepreneurs create new local jobs, but they also generate new wealth and new growth, Low et al. (2005). Finance companies may play a role in attracting and retaining additional economic activity in a community. Additional benefits flow to the community from having additional employment and the resulting spin-off. Fulton and Lou Hammond (1992). Micro-lending program enhances credit access for those small business start-ups that have difficulties in accessing traditional loans mainly because they have no credit history. This program therefore encourage the growth of small and medium enterprises which generate multiplier effects in terms of employment income and population growth.

The greatest strength of Finance companies is their local structure, their sense of community and their focus on individual as an integral part of the community. This may place Finance companies in a position where both place and people centered approaches are combined and increases their ability to focus on community development. Studies by McArthur et al. (1993) and Fairburn et al. (1997) highlight, that community involvement is a key feature of Finance companies and through the work they facilitate and promote capacity building strength and resilience within the community.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Given the focus of this research upon the overview of finance companies in Nepal, the research is an exploratory and analytical type in nature and attempts to analyze the real status of finance company in Nepal and their contribution to the country. For that the research focuses on the secondary data obtained from websites of Nepal Rastraya bank and published materials such as Banking and financial statistics 2012, Economic survey 2069/70, 2004/05 and macroeconomic review 2012. Especially qualitative data are taken for the purpose of the study and financial tools are used for the analysis of the data.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Nepal is a developing country with an agricultural economy. Nearly, half of their populations are living below the poverty line (Economic Survey, 2012). Financial sector can play vital role in Nepalese economy with mobilizes savings and allocates credit across space and time. It provides not only payment services, but more importantly products which enable firms and households to cope with economic uncertainties by hedging, pooling, sharing, and pricing risks.

Financial Institutions Development in Nepal

The table shows the actual financial sector development in Nepal from the last three decade to present. From the above table it has been clear that till 1980s there were only limited financial institutions operating in Nepal. After Government follow the liberalization policy then Number of financial institutions are growing in Nepal which is clearly shown on the table:

Table 1: Number of Financial Institutions in Different Periods

Institutions	1980	1990	2000	2004	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
Commercial banks	2	5	11	29	28	27	31	35	31
Development banks	1	2	2	59	63	79	87	88	88
Insurance companies	1	2	2	21	25	25	25	25	25
Finance companies		2	44	78	77	79	79	69	67
savings and credit co-operative societies			29	72	16	15	16	16	16
Micro credit development bank			7	12	15	18	21	24	25
NGOs licensed by NRB			30	46	45	45	38	36	36

(Sources: Banking and Financial Statistics 2012, Economic Survey 2004)

From the figure below it has been clear that most of the financial institution are only concentrated on the city area. Most of the financial institutions are confined on the Kathmandu valley. So the share of the financial institution on the central development region is higher than the share on the other region. Especially people of the Karnali Zone are still victimized from the service of financial system which shows the financial system imbalance of Nepal.

Table 2: Region Wise Distribution of Financial Institutions' Branches

Type of institution	Development Region				
	Eastern	Central	Western	Mid Western	Far Western
Commercial banks	255	709	256	120	85
development banks	92	260	253	59	23
Micro finance development bank	4	15	3	1	1
Finance companies	35	169	75	11	2
Financial cooperative	4	6	2	2	2
Financial NGOS	6	16	6	7	

(Source: Banking and Financial Statistics, 2012)

The zone wise distribution of finance companies seems to be very unbalanced. During the period of 1995, the services provided by the finance companies were concentrated only the Bagmati, Gandaki, Lumbini and Gandaki Zone. Till April 2013, finance companies are able to expand their services to other 5 Zones. Most of the finance companies are concentrated on the Bagmati zone. Finance Companies are unable to expand their services on Bheri, Karnali, Mahakali, Mechi and Dhaulagiri zones.

Figure 1: Geographical Disbursement of Finance Companies

(Source: Quarterly Economic Bulletin of NRB, Mid April, 2013)

Finance companies invest the funds on different sectors. The investment sectors are Agriculture and forest, Fishery, Mining, Manufacturing, construction, Electricity, metal product and garment, Transportation, communication, Transportation and communication, wholesale and retail, finance, insurance and real estate, hotel and restaurant, other service, consumption loan, local government and others sector. The investment percentage of each sector is 2.51%, .02%, .24%, 7.82%, 13.42%, .20%, 1.33%, 7.77%, 15.80, 12.6%, 2.69%, 4.43%, 8.16%, 0.08% and 23.37% respectively. Finance companies made percent of loan for wholesale and retail sector.

Composition of Assets and Liabilities of Finance Companies

The decrement in number of Finance Companies resulted the total assets/liabilities of the finance companies to shrink by 10.7 percent in Mid - July 2012 and reached to Rs. 112,973 million from 126,617 million in Mid - July 2011. Among the total liabilities deposits held the largest share of 67.4 percent followed by capital fund 13.6 percent others 18.1 percent and borrowings 1.0 percent. The respective share of deposit, capital fund and borrowing were 67.5 percent, 17.2 percent and 11.3 percent in the previous year. On the assets side loan and advances held 59.0 percent of total assets followed by liquid funds 23.8 percent, investment 3.1 percent and others 14.1 percent in Mid - July 2012. The respective share of loan & advances, liquid funds and investments were 68.7 percent, 16.2 percent and 4.5 percent in Mid July 2011.

Figure 2: Structure of Liabilities of Finance Company

Liabilities of finance company

Source: Banking and Financial Statistics 2012

Figure 3: Structure of Assets of Finance Company

Source: Banking and Financial Statistics 2012

Total Deposits of Finance Companies to GDP Ratio

Finance companies accept deposit from public, business from and utilize it on the productive sectors. The Deposit of finance company and GDP ratio is shown on the chart below. The deposit of bank relative to the GDP is constantly growing till 2011. But in 2012 this ratio was decreased. The reason was merger of the many finance companies with banks. Finance companies in deposit also ranked into 2nd position after commercial banks till 2009. But through 2010, development bank lead the finance companies and it is ranked into 3rd position. In 2012 commercial banks hold 80.6% deposit of total deposit of financial sector. Similarly development banks hold 11.8% and finance companies hold 7.1%.

Figure 4: Total Deposit of Finance Company to GDP Ratio

Source: Banking and Financial Statistics 2012

Total Lending of Finance Companies to GDP Ratio

The lending of finance company and GDP ratio is shown on the chart below. The lending of bank relative to the GDP is constantly growing till 2011. But in 2012 this ratio was decreased. The reason was merger of the many finance companies with banks. Finance companies in lending ranked into 2nd position after commercial banks till 2010. But through 2011, development bank lead the finance companies and it is ranked into 3rd position. In 2012 commercial banks hold 77.1% lending of total lending of financial sector. Similarly development banks hold 12.5% and finance companies hold 8.3%.

Figure 5: Total Lending of Finance Company to GDP Ratio

Source: Banking and Financial Statistics 2012

The Ratio of Liquid Liabilities to GDP

The liquid liabilities to GDP ratio is also on rising trend each and every year .It was shrink in 2009 but rose from 2010. Finance companies raised

the liquid liabilities as GDP raised. The ratio was 4.11 percentage on 2012.

Figure 6: Liquid liabilities of Finance company to GDP Ratio

Source: Banking and Financial Statistics 2012

Finance Companies Assets to Total Assets of Banking Sector

Finance company was ranked on second position on total assets till 2009. The first position was occupied by the commercial banks. But after 2010, development bank occupied the second position and finance companies occupied third position. The percentage of finance companies assets on total banking assets from 2001 to 2012 is 5.77%, 5.87%, 6.19%, 7.02%, 6.42%, 7.68%, 9.18%, 11.38%, 8.84%, 10.93%, 10.86% and 8.18% respectively. Total assets portion on 2012 was decreased due to merger of many finance companies to other financial institutions.

Figure 7: Portion of Finance Company Assets on Total Banking Sector:

Source: Banking and Financial Statistics 2012

CONCLUSIONS

The history of the finance company was began in Nepal after the finance company act came into existence in 2042 B.S. There was no finance companies, micro credit development bank, co-operatives till 1990. After 1990s finance companies are began to established in Nepal. But the Geographical disbursement of finance company in Nepal is very unequal. Most of the finance companies are still lies on the Kathmandu valley.

The Nepalese financial system occupied third position on the market share after commercial banks and development banks. The total lending and total deposit ratio of finance companies to GDP are increased each and every year. Which show the positive contribution of the finance companies to the economy of the country? But due to unequal distribution of the services of the finance companies most of the people of the hilly and remote area are at present not able to get services of the finance companies. So policy makers should focus on the situation to uplift the overall economic growth of the country.

The finance companies do the function in General There are no any finance companies that are developed for the special purpose. Nepal is the

developing country with many idle resources. There is huge opportunity when we utilize these resources properly and we become one of the developed countries in the world. Special kinds of finance companies such as finance companies that focus special target area should be established.

Loan that finance companies in Nepal disbursed largely on the wholesale and retail business. Those sectors from where we get excessive return and that add value to the economy such as agriculture, industrial, mines, hydroelectricity, transportation and communication was neglected. The finance companies should give proper attention on those sectors. Moreover, policy maker and regulatory agency should insight on that matter to make rational investment on the priority sector.

After government of Nepal initiates the economic reform program and financial sector reform program, then financial sectors shows the better performance. There are many banks and other financial institutions that started operation in Nepal. As a result many financial institutions started their service in the different part of the country. This is the positive trend of the development of the country. But the innovation on this sector is lacking. In order to become competitive the finance companies need to think to collaborate and merges to make strong capital base. With the globalization, the financial system of the country becomes complex and there is emerging needs of providing better services to become competitive on the market. For that both regulatory agency as well as finance companies needs to become dynamic, innovative and effective. All financial institution should move towards the achieving common goal of making financial sector sound, prudent, efficient and competitive. The NRB should be committed on its work to make financial system competitive, sound, healthy. The NRB should make those kinds of environment so that all financial institution joined their hand to uplift the economy of the country and be able to compete on the global market.

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